

Cultural Loss AfterShocks (CLASh) Andreu Arinyo-i-Prats

We entered the Anthropocene, an era of accelerating socioecological changes¹ which hamper our ability to deal with disasters². In these extreme new transitions, we face multiple compounding challenges without clear answers from a social perspective³. Technological solutions alone are insufficient to face the new realities of the Anthropocene; we need to research, improve, and apply socio-economical strategies, or **‘social technologies’**⁴ to adapt to a changing environment⁵. We do not know how the future climate in the Anthropocene will be⁶, but we do know that any extreme climatic event that impacts present and future societies will have some resemblance to past events⁷ as long as we expand the geographical and temporal scopes^{8,9}. Similarly to extreme events, we need to expand the scope to how societies from the past managed to **effectively pass on the memories of disasters, despite socioecological transitions**. Even societies used to extreme events still experience immense disasters when social change does not effectively remember them. For example, Japan saw many failures leading to the 2011 Tōhoku earthquake catastrophe. Tens of thousands of lives were lost, immense wealth was destroyed, and it triggered the Fukushima nuclear plant disaster which, in itself, had world-wide repercussions. This happened despite coastal Japanese having ample experience with tsunamis, as elements present in the landscape, like tsunami stones exemplify. Afterwards, nearby to Fukushima, the United Nations Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction¹⁰ was signed.

To learn how to make disaster risk reduction practices relevant, **our project aims to investigate the interrelation of memory of disasters with strategies that reduce extreme events’ impact**. Impact-reducing strategies can be examined through the so-called **MPAR** stages of disaster adaptation: 1) **Mitigation**, 2) **Preparation**, 3) **Action/response/coping**, and 4) **Recovery**. For example, in western countries these are well established regarding floods^{6,9,11,12}. However, not unlike the Tōhoku tsunami, flood-related catastrophes continue to occur frequently in the well modeled, well understood Europe and the US, even when landscapes themselves hold the names of past disasters. The 2024 catastrophic floods in Valencia happened close to a river called “the destroyer” (in Arabic) and in 2025 in Texas’ “flash-flood valley” (in English), yet hundreds of lives were lost in both cases. **Our understanding of the mechanisms driving MPAR, particularly from a social perspective, is clearly inadequate**. A major limitation is that MPAR expertise is not shared among administrations across space and time¹³. For example, in the case of flooding at the European level, recent research demonstrates that extreme floods are not rare at the continental level⁹. However, flood disasters still occur because local memory of the event is rare and expertise in disaster risk not kept¹⁴. We lack effective ways of keeping and transferring knowledge, strategies and skills. An area with recent experience of an impact, so far, cannot effectively teach, or help remember, the risk to other areas who lost the memory after long time scales.

Moreover, **social strategies** likely have evolved to be tuned for the **spatio-temporal scales of extreme events onsets and impacts**. Flooding represents fast and geographically constrained disasters, while, at the other end of the spectrum, droughts and harvest failures are slow-paced and geographically widespread¹⁵. These slow events impact societies after several consecutive years of unfavorable conditions, but leave infrastructure intact. **Different onsets of extreme events couple with memories**, shaping the MPAR skills needed to manage future risk. The event onsets imprint **path-specific MPAR expertise, triggering domain specific social memory loss or retention**. This understudied coupling between timings and memories dictates complex decision-making at each MPAR stage⁶.

1. State-of-the-art

In the current rapid Anthropocene transition, there is extensive research dealing with disaster risk reduction from academic to global institutional levels. The **Sendai Framework establishes the basis for global disaster risk reduction**¹⁶. The Framework addresses, among others, how administration and governance are critical in knowledge mobilisation in disaster risk reduction¹⁷. Within the Framework, well-integrated knowledge-based emergency management **information systems is acknowledged to be crucial**, however, a recent review **shows that only limited work in management has been done**¹³.

Numerous research links **catastrophes to erosion of knowledge, well-being and social structures** that have historically underpinned resilience^{7,17-21}. However, responses to extreme events often focus on technologies, prediction, and infrastructure to deal with risk reduction, while neglecting the underlying social structures involved in disaster decision-making²². Governance fails at qualifying and quantifying critical action in environmental management²³, while memories of past disasters, or lack of them, drive communities' risky behaviour^{24,25}. Complicating matters, disasters also cause cultural loss²⁶.

Memory **preservation through regular practice is central to socio-environmental sustainability**²⁷. The recurrence of the practice is key to memory dynamics. Recent studies reveal that expertise decays at different rates, influencing the retention of skills and cultural practices²⁸⁻³⁰. We have shown that different reinforcement strategies at different social and temporal scales can compensate for the decay³¹.

Field research has documented horizontal social memories under frameworks like **Traditional Ecological Knowledge**³² or **Collective Memory**³³. Their spatiotemporal disaster risk reduction strategies range from **weekly cycles to multiple generations, and from square meters to whole ecosystems**³⁴. These strategies might be: altered food practices³⁵, oral traditions³⁶, flock songs³⁷, intergenerational stories³⁸, settlement construction²⁴. Recent modeling also shows generation-dependent and wealth dependent risk-making³⁹. However, these horizontal strategies can be **hard to generalize or transfer due to their local nature, emotional bonds, and qualitative memories**. Moreover, they may adapt slowly to rapidly changing climate and societal conditions⁴⁰.

Policymaking, governance and administrative memory, on the other hand, store risk management memories vertically⁴¹. Unlike horizontal hierarchies, vertical ones **have distinct inherited strategies**, with **geographically-constrained areas and codified temporal actions**. These strategies are determined by their **formal decision-making processes, laws, regulations, training of specialized workforce, quantitative accounting, resource mobilization, storing, transferring of knowledge and expertise and external communication**⁴¹. Unfortunately, research on vertical hierarchies' memory dynamics remains sparse^{42,43}. Modeling is specially lacking, with some efforts focusing on the impact of epidemic spread limited to how abstract "social institutions" deal with coevolution of pathogen and misinformation spread⁴⁴. Fortunately, research shows that these vertical structures are potentially much easier to be accurately described, measured and modeled as hierarchically isolated, modular units relevant for disasters⁴⁵.

2. Research Questions

CLASH aims to answer how social hierarchies **remembering of past disasters makes disaster risk strategies be lost, maintained or become inadequate** when they are needed the most. By studying disaster dynamics and variability, we aim to identify the failures in decision-making at different social hierarchies, specifically when these happened because of the relevant loss of knowledge and skill.

Decision-making landscapes vary from community-wide (horizontal) to specialized administrative levels (vertical). Therefore, the **memories of past disasters at each social level drive disaster risk reduction behavior**^{24,25,46}, and these memories might be differently lost, especially at low frequency, variable impacts, or in a changing environment. Disasters are a crucial both to understand risk reduction and model the internal dynamics of administrations vs communities. CLASH aims to unravel how this spatio-temporal dynamics of extreme events couple with the social structure memories of disasters such that disaster risk management strategies are enhanced, reduced or lost (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. CLASH schema: MPAR practices stored by two social hierarchies' different extreme events temporal onsets

For CLASH' goal, we need to answer: **1)** how to extract qualitative and quantitative data from past records on how MPAR strategies expertise is retained or lost at the Danish, regional, (and global) contexts? **2)** how to model the path-dependent interrelation between impacts of extreme events intensity and variability⁴⁷ and the losing, retention and adaptation of disaster risk-reduction strategies?

3. Project Design

CLASH builds on methodologies from previous projects, including the ECR (CLIOdynamic ARCHAeology) grant led by Felix Riede (FR) and MSCA Cultural Loss Under Emulated Shocks (CLUES) grant, led by Andreu Arinyo-i-Prats (AP). These shared methodologies involve three Work Packages (WP): **WP1 theory building and epistemology**, **WP2 models and Advisory Board**, **WP3 dissemination, outreach and guidelines** (Fig 2).

For **WP1**, a postdoctoral researcher (PR) with the guidance from AP and FR will set the basic definitions and measure units needed to develop the first research question. Since human records are concisely difficult to match with climatic conditions, the PR shall have expertise on climate and environmental history through past documents and archeological records in the Scandinavian context. The PR will be recruited and incorporated to the project after a period of three to four months of hiring. To compensate for the difficulty to define, measure and model data for the human sciences, we will adopt the FAIR principles –Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable– which propose ways to share fuzzy concepts, models, and measure protocols in the social sciences⁴⁸. The epistemological work form **WP1** will allow us to set the ground for planning the effective, empirically-driven methodologies for modeling (**WP2**) **finding meaningful units of memory and impact at the MPAR stages that can be eventually measured across time and space**. For that goal, MPAR stages will be **conceptualized in terms of being used or unused** as a simple binomial outcome, while disasters' impacts will be codified as temporal sequences and estimated relative resources and lives lost. The codification will continuously be shared and updated throught the project in synergy with **WP2**.

Following the principle 'think global, act local', initial focus will be on Denmark, **particularly storm surges and drought events from the first human occupation until the present (WP1)**. Special attention will be made on periods close to the living memory, where multiple proxies of disaster memory can be assessed. **Denmark offers a rich context due to its archeological, historical records, infrastructure, expert access, and cultural narratives of past floods and famines⁴⁷**. These initial narratives will inspire CLASH's epistemology and modelling. First, the PR will inspect Danish administrative records about past impacts in terms of economic and lives lost for food scarcity and floods (1.1). At the community level, memory of these past scarcities might be recorded on a change in food storage strategies, food sources, dietary changes, the use of family and friends' networks, economic

mobility stories and other cultural items³⁸ (1.2). In latter stages, the goal is to assess whether Danish lessons are applicable in the neighboring regions: Baltic, Northern Sea and Central European (1.3). This extension will be used to explore what is needed to **pursue a global perspective**. This last milestone is left as exploratory, as it is complex to achieve since administrative and community strategies **differ widely in “social technologies” and ecologies**, making disaster comparisons challenging (1.4).

In the case of floods in Denmark, relatively accessible MPAR related datasets are stored in infrastructure⁴⁹, administrative records and popular memory⁵⁰. In infrastructure, coastal flooding is often dealt with dikes construction, even when controversial⁵¹. For recent flood events, **dike construction can be easily correlated with multi-proxy data in the form of administrative records, news and folk and oral tradition**⁴⁶. For food scarcity, the 1786-87 famine following poor harvests⁵² and the 1826-1832 mortality crisis⁵³ are recent focal points. A student assistant will help the PR and AP to comb through the archives and infrastructure, encoding a standardized dataset of extreme events temporal onsets and variability, alongside MPAR strategies selected at horizontal or vertical hierarchies.

For WP2, CLASH will employ a model-driven approach to analyze key MPAR mechanisms, which address the second research question. Models create simplified environments to test hypotheses and guide empirical research⁵. We will create a comprehensive **model in three phases**: extreme event onsets, variability and their impacts at two speeds, slow vs fast (2.1); memory dynamics of two hierarchical systems –vertical vs horizontal– experiencing events at different frequencies (2.2); path-dependent simulations to create empirically-motivated recreations of past extreme-event disaster risk reduction cases (2.3). We will adapt evolutionary biology models of environmental forcing that increase complexity⁵⁴, and path-dependent hydrological disaster models⁹. The social component of existing flood impact models is simulated as three abstract, unquantifiable components: trust, risk perception and memory⁵⁵. To compensate for the difficult to quantify these three abstract components, we will focus solely on modeling memory loss/accessibility, while grounding it on empirical metrics of the extreme events memories (2.1), thanks to the work in WP1. Moreover, to make the model empirically justified, **key MPAR elements**⁵⁶ **will be modeled as specific “social technologies”** –like drills⁵⁷, dike construction⁵¹, resources storage⁵⁸ and famine foods knowledge⁵⁹. Each practice will be differently encoded by social hierarchy structure (2.2). Once key mechanisms are identified, their connections across social and environmental scales, plus the definitions and case studies from WP1, **will inform empirically motivated path-dependent loss or retention of MPAR strategies, coupled to the timing of extreme events** (2.3). AP will develop the basic conceptual framework, setting the basis for modeling. The modeling will be consulted with an Advisory Board formed by our collaborators (2.4), experts on

agent-based modeling, cultural evolution, community memory, administration and governance, and disaster risk reduction.

Fig 2: Work Packages (WPs) are shaded for the timeframe to completion; lighter grey represents background work focus. Milestones and deliverables are connected to paper submissions by grey dashed lines. Deliverables (purple) and Milestones (green)

For **WP3, dissemination**, the target will be to submit at least six research papers (3.1) to be peer-reviewed and one white paper (3.3). Following CLASH’ multidisciplinary we will contribute to six European conferences in the areas of disaster risk reduction, climate impacts and administrative information management (3.2). CLASH analysis centers on community-based and administrative strategies; therefore, these two groups shall be the main focus of outreach activities. From the administrative side, Policymakers, NGOs and government officials will be addressed directly with the aim to contribute to a White Paper and relevant forums, especially the Disaster risk management – Europa, in charge of the science-policy interface in Disaster Risk Management (3.3). This strategy aims to capture the relevant actors’ insights and particular perspectives while, in parallel, get them engaged on the research findings and how these can be meaningful for effective Risk Disaster reduction in terms of memory and expertise retention and adaptation. In the case of susceptible communities, outreach is especially crucial, yet challenging since the nature of these collectives is less hierarchical, as for the study design. Other forms of communication will be needed, the outreach activities will be constant through the development of CLASH and will consist of several activities done in parallel: public events, videos, conversations, mnemonic initiatives, press releases, news articles, radio, social media, talks. A webpage will be set up to centralize all project-related information, developments and updates. We will create two videos aimed at the general audience, one showcasing the relevance to understand the effects of the memory of disasters, or their loss, and one summarizing the outcomes and future aims of the research (3.5). General public outreach will be conducted throughout the project, aiming to bridge as much as possible both ends of the studied cases. In Europe, political decisions are often influenced by

public opinion. For the two most outstanding research articles, we will write news articles and publish them in at least two of the general research forums and amplifying platforms aimed at academics. And thanks to the outreach departments at Aarhus University, an advertising campaign will be carried out, in the form of two press releases. Active engagement will be conducted with the amplifiers in the news section of Sciencemag, NewScientist or Scientific American. Social media will be used thorough the project to have constant updates and reach targeted audiences and create links with people who are interested in the research and can potentially contribute to it (3.6).

4. Originality and Impact

CLASh resolves key memory mechanisms used to encode the skills and expertise needed to cope with variability on disasters' impacts, encoded on two social hierarchies. In particular, **CLASh will answer how the loss of key MPAR elements might exacerbate disaster risk, resulting in the ever-present catastrophes.** The project is innovative in that it examines both temporal extremes of disaster—rapid-onset events like floods and slow-onset crises such as food scarcity—within a context of path-dependent socio-environmental change for two different social scales, administrations and communities. Sharing lessons and experiences across susceptible regions could significantly enhance the effectiveness of MPAR management.

We seek to identify both universal and context-specific mechanisms that operate at socio-environmental levels, specifically **knowledge, expertise and skills, adequately couple or not with the timing and onsets of extreme events.** Through a detailed analysis of the Danish context over time and amid social transformations, we aim to uncover the underlying factors that reduce extreme events impacts. We will also explore whether these **factors are consistent across different social contexts and geographies.** The findings of this research are expected to enhance our ability to communicate the impacts of disasters across time and space^{60,61}. The lessons learned may also inform the future training of individuals at administrative, policymaking, governments, and community levels for future risk by detecting when meaningful knowledge and skill (cultural strategies) are lost, inaccessible or unsuitable for the new socioecological conditions.

If we identify which cross-scale mechanisms exist or are missing, their interrelations, and how to model and codify the strengths and weaknesses of MPAR stages across socio-environmental scales, these can be used to reduce the impact of extreme events in a changing world benefiting future generations. The need to **define language, build models, measures and comparisons** between different social hierarchies and geographies, at the end of the project, enables us to form the basis of a system that aims to extend beyond CLASh research questions⁵⁶. Ultimately, we hope our results will provide effective tools and vocabulary that enables this knowledge to be shared globally.